

Confirming Correct, Missing the Rest: LLM Tutoring Agents Struggle Where Feedback Matters Most

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Abstract

Effective tutoring requires distinguishing optimal (expert-path), valid-alternative (valid but suboptimal), and incorrect student solutions, a distinction central to intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) yet untested for LLM-based tutors. As LLMs are increasingly explored as conversational complements to ITS for scalable feedback, evaluating their diagnostic precision is essential. We benchmark seven LLMs as feedback agents in propositional logic using knowledge-graph-derived ground truth across 10,836 solution-feedback pairs¹ and three prompt-level feedback conditions. Our analysis shows that models achieve near-ceiling performance on optimal steps but systematically over-reject valid-alternative reasoning and over-validate incorrect solutions, precisely where adaptive tutoring matters most. These failure modes persist regardless of solution context or model capability, indicating architectural rather than informational limits. Accurate classification does not reliably translate into pedagogically actionable feedback, exposing a gap between diagnostic judgment and instructional effectiveness. LLMs thus cannot resolve the assistance dilemma without ITS-grounded mechanisms; they are better positioned within hybrid systems that combine LLM flexibility with ITS student modeling.

1 Introduction

Effective tutoring requires recognizing not just whether student solutions are correct, but whether they reflect sound reasoning that warrants encouragement or strategic guidance towards more efficient approaches (Gupta et al., 2025). In structured reasoning domains like propositional logic, students may produce optimal next steps that follow expert authored paths to conclusion, apply valid but suboptimal inference rules (*valid-alternative*

steps), or make errors entirely (Maniktala et al., 2023). Examples illustrated in Fig 4 and Fig 5.

Distinguishing these cases has direct pedagogical consequences: misclassifying valid student reasoning as incorrect can undermine their confidence and discourage productive exploration, while validating all incorrect steps without guiding toward more efficient solutions reinforces inefficient strategies. This trade-off is characterized in the learning sciences as the *assistance dilemma* (Koedinger and Alevan, 2007).

Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) enable step-level diagnosis through explicitly modeled solution spaces (VanLehn, 2011). But they require expert-authored solution graphs for each problem, limiting scalability to new domains (Weitekamp et al., 2020), and may offer limited support for the conversational, exploratory dialogue students need when reasoning diverges from anticipated paths (Zerkouk and Chikhaoui, 2025).

Large language models (LLMs) directly address these limitations through conversational flexibility, cross-domain generalization, and scalable feedback without per-problem authoring (Reddig et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2025), making them natural candidates for complementing ITS. Yet without external grounding, LLMs hallucinate (Liu et al., 2025a) and reveal solutions rather than scaffold reasoning (Macina et al., 2023), limiting their reliability. Role-specialized feedback pipelines with grounding in expert solution information show promise for improving diagnostic precision (Phung et al., 2024; Guo et al., 2024). Whether these mechanisms enable the fine-grained diagnostic distinctions essential for effective tutoring remains an open question, one that ultimately determines whether LLMs can meaningfully complement intelligent tutoring systems in structured reasoning domains.

We address this gap through a large-scale evaluation of LLM feedback in propositional logic, a structured reasoning domain in which the three-

¹https://github.com/anonymouspaper64-debug/anonymous_paper.git

way distinction between optimal, valid-alternative, and incorrect steps carries direct pedagogical implications. Unlike prior LLM-based tutoring evaluations that rely on binary correctness schemes (Gupta et al., 2025; Borchers and Shou, 2025), thereby collapsing distinctions central to intelligent tutoring systems (Alevan et al., 2009; VanLehn, 2006), we ground this three-way classification in a knowledge-graph-based solution space derived from a real tutoring system that encodes all valid inference paths. This enables the first benchmark for step-level evaluation of LLM tutoring feedback across multiple valid solution trajectories. Using this framework, we evaluate 10,836 LLM-simulated next-step solutions with knowledge-graph-grounded evaluation enabling objective evaluation of corresponding feedback across seven models and three prompt-level feedback conditions that vary only in the solution context available to feedback agent.

Despite this controlled and fine-grained evaluation setup, accurate solution classification alone does not guarantee pedagogically appropriate feedback. The assistance dilemma applies equally to LLMs, which may correctly identify solution quality yet fail to provide guidance that supports learning, instead defaulting to confirmation or error flagging. Understanding whether LLMs can bridge this gap, and what governs their ability to do so, motivates our three research questions:

RQ1: How accurately do LLM feedback agents classify single step logic proofs solutions as optimal, valid-alternative, or incorrect, and what systematic error patterns emerge?

RQ2: What model-level and problem-level factors govern classification accuracy across optimal, valid-alternative, and incorrect solutions?

RQ3: What is the pedagogical quality of LLM-generated feedback, and how does it relate to three-way classification accuracy?

Our findings reveal that LLMs systematically over-reject valid-alternative reasoning and over-validate incorrect solutions regardless of solution context or model capability, and that accurate solution classification does not reliably translate into pedagogically actionable feedback. Together, these results indicate that current LLMs cannot resolve the assistance dilemma without ITS-grounded diagnostic mechanisms, informing how LLMs might be integrated into replace adaptive tutoring systems.

2 Related Work

LLMs in Tutoring LLMs show promise for diagnosing student errors (Reddig et al., 2025) and supporting self-regulation (Chen et al., 2025), yet tutoring-specific evaluations show they cannot reliably locate reasoning errors even with reference solutions (Liu et al., 2025b; Jia et al., 2024). Role-specialized feedback pipelines, where one agent generates feedback and a downstream agent verifies it, address some of these limitations by improving precision (Phung et al., 2024) and reducing over-praise (Guo et al., 2024), yet verifiers may propagate rather than correct initial errors (Guo et al., 2024). Prior evaluations further show that LLMs exhibit minimal adaptivity to tutoring context (Borchers and Shou, 2025) and fail on partially correct responses where students most need guidance (Mahdavi et al., 2025). Critically, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work jointly evaluates whether accurate diagnostic judgments translate into pedagogically appropriate instructional actions, that this work aims to investigate.

LLM-Simulated Students Evaluating tutoring feedback requires student solutions spanning the full range of response types, including valid-alternative solutions systematically underrepresented in real interaction logs (Maniktala et al., 2023). LLM-simulated solutions have emerged as an established methodology for this coverage problem. Mannekote et al. (Mannekote et al., 2025) validate that LLMs can reliably simulate human learner actions in open-ended learning environments. Phung et al. (Phung et al., 2024) use LLM-generated responses to evaluate feedback pipelines in programming tutoring. Furthermore, Lu and Wang (Lu and Wang, 2024) verify that LLMs can simulate student answers to multiple-choice questions that are aligned with their profiles and highly correlated to real student answers. Benedetto et al. (Benedetto et al., 2024) validate LLMs reliably simulate real student answers of different skill levels across different educational domains. In this work, simulation is additionally necessitated by a technical constraint: our tutoring system logs lack reasoning traces, rendering real interaction data insufficient for evaluating reasoning validity at the step level. On the other hand, the logic reasoning dataset by (Zhang et al., 2022) only provides benchmark in natural language limiting objective evaluation step and branching level. To address these, we combine LLM-simulated solutions with

knowledge-graph-grounded evaluation, enabling objective verification of reasoning validity across multiple solution paths.

ITS Adaptivity and LLMs In structured reasoning domains, multiple valid solution paths are prevalent (Große and Renkl, 2006; Maniktala et al., 2023). Traditional ITS handle this through manually specified solution graphs (Alevan et al., 2009), explicitly encoding optimal and valid-alternative paths that restricts evaluation to only pre-authored problems. While scalable, LLMs only marginally mimic ITS adaptivity (Borchers and Shou, 2025) and struggle to evaluate sub-steps where multiple correct solutions exist (Gupta et al., 2025). Whether LLM tutoring agents can replicate ITS-style adaptivity in reliably distinguishing optimal, valid-alternative, and incorrect responses remains untested, and is the central question this work addresses.

Evaluation Benchmarks Among logic reasoning benchmarks, ProofWriter (Tafjord et al., 2020) assesses only final proof validity, obscuring whether models apply inference rules correctly at each step. FOLIO (Han et al., 2024) provides expert-authored first-order logic problems but penalizes semantically valid alternative derivations, while ProntoQA (Saparov and He, 2023) enables controlled evaluation through synthetic reasoning chains but cannot capture branching decision points where multiple inference rules may apply. On the other hand LogicLearner (Inamdar et al., 2025) provide students with guided practice on only basic Logic problems and the benchmark data is not available. None of these support evaluation of feedback quality for intermediate steps when valid alternative solutions exist, the gap this work addresses.

3 Dataset and Knowledge Graph

3.1 Task Formulation

A propositional logic proof problem is a tuple (\mathcal{P}, C) , where $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ is a set of premises (statements assumed to be true) and C is the target conclusion. A proof state $\sigma = (\mathcal{P}, I, C)$ captures progress through the proof, where I is the ordered set of intermediate statements derived so far by applying inference rules $r \in R$ to statements in $\mathcal{P} \cup I$, with $I = \emptyset$ initially (complete set of logic inference rules in Appendix B).

We investigate single-step prediction: deriving optimal next step (statement) in exactly one rule application from $\mathcal{P} \cup I$ that minimizes remaining derivation distance to C . We restrict this task to

only single next step prediction and respective feedback generation and evaluation.

3.2 Dataset

To generate single step solution-feedback pairs, we use 516 unique proof states extracted from interaction logs of a propositional logic tutoring system deployed in an undergraduate Discrete Mathematics course at a large U.S. university (Barnes and Stamper, 2008). States are drawn from 32 proof problems across five practice levels of varying difficulty (introductory through expert), providing context specific and on-demand hints we call solution context (Spring 2023). Levels 1 (pre-test) and 7 (post-test) are excluded because they do not provide hints. Each instance is unique at triple level (\mathcal{P}, I, C) , to ensure each instance represents a distinct proof state. An example proof state is illustrated in Fig 2 and Fig 12. Appendix 4 summarizes the data distribution across tutor difficulty levels. Tutoring system illustrations are present in Appendix D.

3.3 Knowledge Graph Construction

To provide ground truth that captures all logically valid solution paths in our dataset, we encode the complete solution space for each of the 32 problems as a knowledge graph K . Formally, $K = (\Sigma, E)$ where Σ is the set of all reachable proof states and $(\sigma_i, \sigma_j) \in E$ represents a valid single-step inference. σ_j is obtained from σ_i by deriving a new statement \hat{s} via rule $r \in R$ applied to parent statements from $\mathcal{P} \cup I_i$, such that $I_j = I_i \cup \{\hat{s}\}$. The graph is rooted at $\sigma_0 = (\mathcal{P}, \emptyset, C)$ and terminates at σ^* where $C \in I^*$. Given a finite premise set and closed rule set R of 15 propositional inference rules, all reachable derivations are enumerable via forward chaining, making this encoding exhaustive by construction (Barnes and Stamper, 2008).

Each edge $(\sigma_i, \sigma_j) \in E$ in the KG is annotated with the inference rule and respective parent statements in σ_i used to derive the next step \hat{s} in σ_j . This annotation is necessary because a predicted step \hat{s} may be symbolically valid yet inferentially unjustified if attributed to an incorrect rule or unsupported parent statements. For example, a model predicting C via Modus Ponens must correctly identify both $(A \rightarrow C)$ and A as parents; a prediction that produces a valid next step but misattributes the rule or parent statements is flagged as incorrect regardless of symbolic next step validity. Edge-level annotation thus enables verification of both what was

derived and how the derivation is justified.

Building on this edge-level annotation, distance to conclusion is defined as $d(\sigma) = \min_{\pi: \sigma \rightsquigarrow \sigma^*} |\pi|$, computed via breadth-first search over K . To enable three-way classification, a next step, \hat{s} from state σ_t is classified as one of three categories:

Optimal (i.e., following an expert-authored path) if $(\sigma_t, \hat{\sigma}_{t+1}) \in E$ and $d(\hat{\sigma}_{t+1}) = d(\sigma_t) - 1$: a valid inference that strictly reduces distance to the conclusion.

Valid-alternative if $(\sigma_t, \hat{\sigma}_{t+1}) \in E$ but $d(\hat{\sigma}_{t+1})$ does not reduce the distance to the conclusion.

Incorrect if $(\sigma_t, \hat{\sigma}_{t+1}) \notin E$, meaning \hat{s} not derivable under any valid inference rule per K .

Unlike prior benchmarks relying on binary correctness, our KG encodes all logically valid paths including valid-alternative trajectories, enabling a principled three-way diagnostic distinction central to evaluation. These three categories are not merely diagnostic labels, each warrants a distinct instructional response that feedback agents must produce to generate pedagogically effective feedback (Sec 4.2).

4 Methods

4.1 Experimental Pipeline

To construct next step solution-feedback pairs, we use LLM-simulated next step solutions generated using proof states from our dataset (Sec 3.2) and paired with respective LLM feedback generated across three prompt-level role-specialized feedback conditions (Section 4.2). Figure 1 summarizes the full experimental pipeline.

The interaction logs from the tutoring system only record the predicted next step, inference rule, and parent statements, with no reasoning trace. Without reasoning trace it is impossible to evaluate whether LLM feedback agents can effectively assess and diagnose reasoning validity along with symbolic correctness. Hence, to account for reasoning trace, we used LLM simulation which is an established methodology for tutoring evaluation (Mannekote et al., 2025; Phung et al., 2024), to generate next step solutions along with reasoning.

We evaluate seven LLMs spanning reasoning-augmented models (GPT-o3, DeepSeek-R1, Qwen-3-32B) and standard instruction-tuned models (GPT-4.1, Gemini-1.5-Pro, LLaMA-3.3-70B, Mistral-Large), covering both proprietary and open-weight families to enable comparative analysis across capability levels relevant to educational de-

Figure 1: Experimental pipeline. Blue: data extracted from Logic Tutor. Red: LLM-simulated solutions. Yellow: feedback agents with varying solution context (dashed boxes indicate available information). Green: evaluation outputs.

ployment. Each model serves in two roles: as a student simulator to generate next step solution and as a feedback agent to evaluate the feedback (Section 4.2). Using the same model in both roles avoids bias from mismatched model pairs and reflects deployment scenarios where a single model handles both tasks. This design enables model-level analysis of both classification accuracy and feedback quality across the same capability profile, directly addressing RQ1 and RQ2.

As a student simulator, each model receives the proof state $\sigma = (\mathcal{P}, I, C)$ from dataset, and produces a structured next-step solution comprising: (1) a predicted step in symbolic form, (2) the inference rule applied, (3) parent statements used, and (4) a natural language reasoning trace, prompt is provided in Fig 19. Models are prompted to produce the most appropriate next step given the current proof state without explicit instruction to produce a particular solution category. The solution category (optimal, valid-alternative, or incorrect), is determined after generation by verifying the predicted step against the KG (Section 3.3).

As a feedback condition, each model is then prompted to evaluate simulated solutions under each of the three conditions, yielding $516 \times 7 \times 3 = 10,836$ solution-feedback pairs: 516 proof states, seven LLMs, three feedback conditions. This scale ensures sufficient coverage across solution categories, reasoning traces, and conditions for the classification analysis in RQ1. Each pair constitutes one classification instance: a single next-step solution and reasoning trace by one model evaluated by one feedback agent from the same model under one condition. To ensure a fair comparison, we reuse the simulated solutions from each model across all of its feedback conditions. Prompt templates for feedback agents are provided in Appendix J.

4.2 Feedback Conditions

Accurate diagnostic classification alone is not sufficient for effective tutoring and requires translating each judgment into a pedagogically appropriate instructional action. For example **Optimal** steps may only warrant confirmation and encouragement to proceed further; however, **Valid-alternative** steps require acknowledgment of sound reasoning with redirection toward efficiency; and **Incorrect** steps necessitates error identification and corrective guidance (VanLehn, 2006). To evaluate whether LLM feedback agents can meet these requirements, and whether doing so depends on solution context, we operationalize three prompt-level conditions differing only in expert solution information each agent receives, holding task, architecture, and all other constraints constant. Each condition represents a distinct tutoring role:

- **Peer** receives only the next step in symbolic form, representing a peer in real life who knows the answer but lacks effective reasoning. This minimal context tests whether correctness-only grounding suffices for accurate classification and pedagogically appropriate feedback generation.
- **Teacher** represents a real life teacher with complete solution, including the inference rule and parent statements. This tests whether full derivational context improves diagnostic accuracy and feedback quality beyond the Peer condition.
- **Judge** receives the complete derivation along with the Peer’s feedback, and represents a teacher who reviews teaching assistants feedback for improvement. This is consistent with evaluation, validation, orchestration loop in ITS (Rodrigues et al., 2025) and aligns with LLM-as-Judge paradigm (Zheng et al., 2023). This condition tests whether a downstream verification step can correct upstream diagnostic errors and improve pedagogical feedback quality.

Figure 2 illustrates the information available to each feedback condition for a representative proof state. All feedback agents are prompt-level conditions, rather than distinct model architectures. All conditions use the same prompt template, differing only in the information provided about the expert solution and upstream feedback. Pedagogical constraints were held constant across conditions: agents were instructed to scaffold reasoning without revealing answers, acknowledge correct reasoning before addressing errors, and limit feedback to 2–3 sentences (VanLehn, 2006). This design

Proof State (extracted from logic tutoring system)	
Premises: 1. $((F \vee G) \rightarrow H)$, 2. $(I \vee F)$, 3. $(\neg I \wedge J)$	
Derived: 4. $\neg I$ [Simp : (3)]; 5. F [DS : (2), (4)]	
Conclusion: H	
LLM-simulated solution	
Next Step: $(F \vee G)$ Rule: Add Parents: F	
Reasoning trace: “The step $(F \vee G)$ is optimal because it directly constructs the antecedent of the first premise...”	
Expert solution (extracted from tutoring system) - “Derive $(F \vee G)$ from F using the Addition rule.”	
Feedback Agent	Solution Context
Peer	“ $(F \vee G)$ ”
Teacher	“Derive $(F \vee G)$ from F using the Addition rule.”
Judge	“Derive $(F \vee G)$... Addition rule” + Peer feedback

Figure 2: Exemplar proof state with an LLM-simulated solution (KG-verified as Optimal) and solution context available to each feedback condition.

isolates information access as the primary independent variable to enable direct comparison of whether richer solution context improves diagnostic accuracy addressing *RQ1*, or account for better feedback quality, addressing *RQ3*.

5 Evaluation

5.1 Automated Metrics

To address *RQ1* and *RQ2*, we compute classification accuracy and identify factors governing misclassification using automated metrics derived from our KG ground truth.

Classification accuracy (RQ1) Each feedback agent is explicitly prompted to classify the solution as Optimal, Valid-alternative, or Incorrect. We compare this explicit classification against the KG-derived ground truth label generated via the verification procedure described in Section 3.3. Because models may respond differently across solution categories, we report per-category F1 scores rather than overall accuracy. The two horns of the assistance dilemma manifest in the analysis as distinct misclassification failure modes. We operationalize these as two conditional error rates that capture pedagogically distinct harms that aggregate F1 scores obscure:

Over-rejection: rate at which valid-alternative solutions are incorrectly labeled as incorrect, risking discouragement of productive reasoning.

Over-validation: rate at which incorrect solutions are labeled as valid, risking reinforcement of misconceptions.

Factors affecting misclassification (RQ2) To further identify what model-level and problem-

level factors govern classification accuracy, and whether their effects differ across solution categories, we analyze four factors:

Model vs. solution context: We compare variance (η^2) explained by model selection versus feedback condition to determine whether diagnostic accuracy is governed by model capability or solution context.

Step complexity: To isolate reasoning difficulty from model-level diagnostic failures, we test whether next step symbolic complexity, computed as a weighted function of logical operators and their nesting depth, predicts misclassification. More on computing symbolic complexity (App F.1).

Distance to goal: To analyze whether remaining distance to the conclusion affects over-rejection and over-validation, we analyzed distance vs. error rates to explain diagnostic failures at specific stages of the derivation (App F.2).

Inference rule: We compared F1 scores by inference rule, identifying whether specific rules are systematically misdiagnosed across models.

5.2 Human Evaluation (RQ3)

To further establish whether better solution classification results in pedagogically appropriate feedback, two annotators independently evaluated feedback quality on a sample of 100 solution-feedback pairs per condition. The samples were drawn from 200 distinct proof states stratified across solution categories and difficulty levels. Annotators included a graduate researcher and an instructor with expertise in the logic tutoring system, ensuring familiarity with the proof domain and pedagogical aspects of feedback. Following an initial calibration phase, rubric definitions were iteratively refined, and disagreements were resolved through discussion to reach consensus until inter-rater reliability exceeded Cohen’s $\kappa > 0.80$ overall and per dimension. Annotators then independently coded all remaining samples.

The rubrics include four dimensions adapted from Maurya et al. (2025) (Table 6): *Correctness* (logical accuracy of feedback), *Error Identification* (precision in diagnosing errors), *Revealing* (degree of solution disclosure), and *Actionability* (clarity of guidance). These four dimensions directly operationalize the solution classification from pedagogical feedback dissociation central to RQ3.

6 Results

We organize results around three research questions. First, we report classification accuracy and systematic error patterns (RQ1). Next, we examine factors, including model selection, feedback conditions, step complexity, distance to goal, and inference rule, to affect classification accuracy (RQ2). Last, we assess whether accurate solution classification translates into pedagogically appropriate feedback (RQ3).

6.1 RQ1: Classification Accuracy and Error Patterns

Table 1 presents classification scores (F1) across models and feedback conditions. All models achieved near-ceiling performance on optimal student solutions ($F1 : 94 - 99\%$) but struggled with valid-alternatives ($F1 : 0 - 76\%$) and incorrect solutions ($F1 : 4 - 55\%$).

Across the student solutions, models exhibited distinct classification patterns. GPT-4.1 and GPT-o3 showed balanced but moderate performance across valid alternatives. Gemini and Deepseek achieved the highest valid-alternative score ($F1 : 70 - 76\%$) but poor incorrect detection ($F1 : 4 - 19\%$). Conversely, Llama-3 showed the opposite pattern: near-zero valid-alternative classification ($F1 : 0 - 17\%$) but the highest incorrect detection among all models ($F1 : 45 - 55\%$).

Table 1 quantifies these patterns through conditional error probabilities. Gemini and Deepseek showed high over-validation (69 – 71%) but low over-rejection (13 – 17%), treating most student solutions as valid-alternative regardless of correctness. LLaMA 3 showed the opposite: 91% over-rejection but only 6% over-validation, rejecting nearly all non-optimal student solutions. GPT-4.1 and GPT-o3 showed moderate rates of both error types (29 – 41%). These classification patterns have direct pedagogical consequences. Over-rejection risks discouraging productive exploration and penalizing sound reasoning that diverges from the expert path (Maniktala et al., 2023); over-validation reinforces misconceptions and denies corrective feedback essential for learning (VanLehn, 2006).

6.2 RQ2: Factors Affecting Classification

Given the substantial variation in classification accuracy across models, we examined what factors impact misclassification.

Table 1: Classification F1 and error rates by model. P = Peer, T = Teacher, J = Judge. OR = Over-Rejection, OV = Over-Validation. CIs: $\pm 5-8\%$. $^\dagger N < 50$.

Model	Opt.	Valid-Alt.			Incorrect			OR	OV
	Avg	P	T	J	P	T	J	(%)	(%)
GPT-4.1	0.99	0.55	0.57	0.49	0.42	0.40	0.41	38.57	28.65
GPT-o3	0.99	0.48	0.55	0.45	0.38	0.40	0.40	40.50	29.97
Gemini-1.5 Pro	0.99	0.70	0.73	0.72	0.09	0.04	0.08	12.77	70.55
DeepSeek	0.99	0.74	0.76	0.74	0.09	0.12	0.19	17.12	68.60
Qwen	0.99	0.58	0.42	0.54	0.11	0.07	0.12	54.65	28.30
Mistral	0.95	0.58	0.47	0.52	0.15	0.09	0.12	26.28	54.37
Llama 3 [†]	0.94	0.03	0.00	0.17	0.48	0.55	0.45	91.07	6.47

Model Selection vs. Feedback Conditions Model selection explains the majority of observed variance in classification accuracy ($\eta^2 > 0.95$, $p < .001$), while feedback conditions had a negligible effect ($\eta^2 < .01$). (Table 1) shows that increased information access did not improve the classification of valid-alternative or incorrect student solutions. This indicates that a richer solution context does not improve diagnostic accuracy when student solutions diverge from the expected path.

Step Complexity: Because feedback conditions showed a negligible effect on classification ($\eta^2 < .01$), we pooled feedback agents across models to maximize statistical power for analyzing complexity effects on classification. However, complexity predicted misclassification only for Optimal solutions: feedback agents misclassified more complex steps ($M = 2.46$) than correctly classified ones ($M = 1.95$; $p < .05$). For valid-alternative and incorrect student solutions, complexity did not predict errors ($p > .08$), feedback agents rejected simpler valid-alternatives ($M = 2.97$) more often than complex ones ($M = 3.62$), suggesting rejection is driven by deviation from the expert path rather than step difficulty.

Complexity vs. error rate plot in (Fig 9) show that LLaMA over-rejection approaches 100% at complexity tier 3-4, while DeepSeek and Gemini over-validation persists across all tiers, confirming model-level rather than difficulty-driven failure.

Distance to Conclusion: Distance vs. error rate analysis (Fig 10) reveals over-rejection rates are highest at Distance tier 1-2, meaning agents most frequently penalize valid-alternative reasoning when solutions are closest to the conclusion.

Inference Rule: The analysis of inference rule vs. F1 scores (Fig 11) shows classification failures concentrate on structurally complex rules (MT, CD, DeM), with LLaMA showing minimal gains across nearly all rule types, while Gemini and DeepSeek

Table 2: Mean complexity (correct vs. incorrect steps)

Type	Corr.	Incorr.	Diff.	N
Optimal	1.95	2.46	+0.51*	1189
Valid Alt.	3.62	2.97	-0.65	816
Incorrect	3.91	3.78	-0.13	1619

* $p < .05$ (Mann-Whitney U)

Figure 3: Mean feedback quality scores across rubric dimensions (N=100).

score consistently highest.

Taken together, these findings indicate that classification failures when solutions deviate from provided context, are driven by model-level diagnostic limits that persist regardless of solution context, step complexity, proximity to the conclusion, or inference rule type.

6.3 RQ3: Feedback Quality

To assess whether accurate solution classification translates into pedagogically appropriate feedback, we report aggregate scores and LLM responses.

Overall patterns: Figure 3 summarizes mean rubric scores (1-3 scale). Error Identification here measures whether feedback precisely identified the reasoning flaw, distinct from classification accuracy (RQ1), which captures only categorical judgment. Across agents, scores were lowest on Error Identification and Actionability, indicating that feedback frequently failed to diagnose errors or provide clear guidance, consistent with automated analysis (Sec 6.1 and 6.2).

Qualitative analysis clarifies this pattern: although our prompts instructed feedback agents to acknowledge correct reasoning *before addressing errors*, agents often praise solutions without subsequently identifying errors or offering actionable direction. This produced feedback that was encouraging, but pedagogically misleading, particularly

for incorrect and valid-alternative solutions.

Peer feedback: Peer agents consistently scored lowest among the three feedback agents across all human-evaluated dimensions (Figure 3). Restricted access to solution context leads to peer agents frequently restating student reasoning or offering vague feedback without diagnosing errors or specifying further guidance. (response in Fig 13).

Teacher and Judge feedback: Unlike Peer agents, Teacher and Judge agents were better at error identification. However, their feedback penalized valid-alternative reasoning by directing students towards the provided solution context, a pattern most evident for more complex inference rules also responsible for errors discussed in 6.2 (Fig 11). Agents showed strong preference for simpler inference rules even to acknowledge valid-alternatives (Fig 14 shows example feedback).

Verification Condition Contrary to the LLM-as-Judge gains identified in literature (Zheng et al., 2023), Judge feedback did not consistently improve feedback quality. When Peers missed errors, Judge agents typically propagated rather than corrected errors (Figure 17), consistent with RQ2 findings that model selection dominates ($\eta^2 > .95$) while feedback conditions have a negligible effect. Rather than independently evaluating the reasoning, Judge agents anchored to Peer’s framing, inheriting same categorical biases that produced the initial error.

7 Discussion

RQ1: Our results show that LLMs demonstrate limited sensitivity to valid-alternative solutions, defaulting to surface-level pattern matching against available solution context rather than reasoning validity. Collapsed entirely by binary correctness schemes, over-rejection and over-validation failure modes are only separable through the three-way KG-grounded framework, underscoring why evaluation methodology matters as much as model capability (VanLehn, 2006; Koedinger et al., 2012).

RQ2: Our analysis shows that model capability accounts for classification errors far more than feedback conditions, indicating that diagnostic failures are architectural rather than informational. LLMs generate confirmatory judgments when solutions align with the optimal path but show systematic bias once reasoning deviates, regardless of solution context provided. Improving diagnostic accuracy therefore requires capability-level advances, not prompt or information-access design (Stamper

et al., 2024; Venugopalan et al., 2025).

RQ3: Translating diagnostic judgments into pedagogically effective actions remains a core challenge. Agents with greater solution context produced overly directive feedback; less-informed agents produced open-ended responses lacking diagnostic grounding. This mirrors the assistance dilemma: excessive directness constrains learning while insufficient guidance fails to support progress (Koedinger and Alevan, 2007). Prompt-level layering alone cannot ensure adaptive feedback; effective verification requires an independent classification signal, precisely the grounded diagnostic mechanism ITS student modeling provides.

Implications for Education: LLMs address ITS limitations in conversational flexibility and cross-domain scalability (Reddig et al., 2025); however, their diagnostic limits, specifically the inability to distinguish valid-alternative from incorrect reasoning, risk pedagogically misleading feedback, precisely what ITS student modeling mechanisms are designed to prevent (Venugopalan et al., 2025). These results confirm that linguistic fluency alone does not ensure pedagogical effectiveness (Shetye, 2024). A principled hybrid architecture that uses LLMs for open-ended scaffolding and dialogue, while delegating diagnostic classification to ITS-grounded models, offers combining flexibility with the precision required for adaptive tutoring.

8 Conclusion

This study benchmarked LLMs as step-level tutors in propositional logic, jointly assessing diagnostic accuracy and respective feedback quality across feedback conditions controlling for solution information access. Our results show that LLMs reliably confirmed optimal steps because of solution access but struggled with diagnosing reasoning when reasoning deviated from optimal solutions such as valid-alternative and incorrect, precisely where adaptive tutoring is most critical. Solution classification failures persisted regardless of solution context or model capability, and accurate classification did not reliably translate into pedagogically actionable feedback. These findings indicate that current LLMs cannot resolve the assistance dilemma without ITS-grounded diagnostic mechanisms, and are better positioned as components within hybrid systems that integrate established student modeling and scaffolding mechanisms.

Limitations and Future Directions

This study targets propositional logic by design: KG-grounded exhaustive enumeration of valid inference paths is feasible in this formal domain and provides the principled ground truth that evaluation requires. Extending this evaluation methodology to less-structured domains is a direction for future work. Proof states were drawn from a single undergraduate course at one institution, and LLM-simulated solutions may not fully capture authentic student reasoning diversity; a planned extension investigates whether LLMs can reliably replicate actual student solution patterns. Additionally, the scale of the study and feedback nuances precluded systematic analysis of cases where models correctly classify a solution yet still produce inaccurate, vague, revealing, or unactionable feedback, a gap we aim to address in follow-on work. Future directions include adaptive ITS that combines LLM conversational capabilities with ITS-grounded scaffolding, supporting students on proof problems beyond pre-authored problem sets.

Ethics Statement

Student interaction data was collected under IRB approval with informed consent. All data was anonymized before analysis. Our LLM-based Evaluation does not involve human subjects beyond annotators, who serve as researchers for the tutoring system used for data generation in this study, as well as co-authors of this study.

Reproducibility

Code and data will be released upon publication. All experiments use temperature 0.0 to ensure deterministic, reproducible results, prioritizing controlled comparison over response diversity. While real-world tutoring systems might benefit from non-zero temperature, our evaluation focuses on measuring the systematic effects of multi-agent architectures under controlled conditions. Model specifications and prompts appear in Appendices H and J.

AI Usage Disclosure

This work studies and evaluates large language models as research objects. We utilized large language models as assistive tools during manuscript preparation, including formatting guidelines and brainstorming organization, mainly, and paraphrasing on a need basis only. We did not use any AI

tools for designing, implementing, or executing this research study. All the claims, analyses, hypotheses, and conclusions are developed, verified, and reviewed by the authors. Moreover, no AI tool was used for generating or labeling data, making judgments about data, or making any scientific claims. All implementations were reviewed, validated, and finalized by the authors. The authors take full responsibility for the correctness, originality, and integrity of the work.

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A Example Solution Paths

Please refer to Figure 4 and 5.

Figure 4: Example Optimal Solution Path

Figure 5: Example Sub-optimal Solution Path

B Inference Rule List

We employ a fixed set of propositional inference rules used in Logic Tutor for the dataset. The short names were used for consistent response generation and evaluation. The complete list of inference rules, along with short names and derivations are provided below in Table 3.

Table 3: Propositional inference rules used in this work.

Abbrev.	Rule Name	Form
MP	Modus Ponens	$P \rightarrow Q, P \Rightarrow Q$
MT	Modus Tollens	$P \rightarrow Q, \neg Q \Rightarrow \neg P$
Conj	Conjunction	$P, Q \Rightarrow P \wedge Q$
Simp	Simplification	$P \wedge Q \Rightarrow P$ (or Q)
Add	Addition	$P \Rightarrow P \vee Q$
DS	Disjunctive Syllogism	$P \vee Q, \neg P \Rightarrow Q$
HS	Hypothetical Syllogism	$P \rightarrow Q, Q \rightarrow R \Rightarrow P \rightarrow R$
Impl	Implication	$P \rightarrow Q \equiv \neg P \vee Q$
DN	Double Negation	$P \equiv \neg \neg P$
CP	Contraposition	$P \rightarrow Q \equiv \neg Q \rightarrow \neg P$
Com	Commutation	$P \vee Q \equiv Q \vee P$
Assoc	Associativity	$(P \vee Q) \vee R \equiv P \vee (Q \vee R)$
Dist	Distribution	$P \wedge (Q \vee R) \equiv (P \wedge Q) \vee (P \wedge R)$
CD	Constructive Dilemma	$(P \rightarrow Q), (R \rightarrow S), P \vee R \Rightarrow Q \vee S$
Equiv	Equivalence	$P \leftrightarrow Q \equiv (P \rightarrow Q) \wedge (Q \rightarrow P)$

C Dataset Distribution

Table 4: Dataset distribution across practice levels (2-6)

Difficulty	Proof States	Avg. Statements
2 (Introductory)	48	5.86
3 (Basic)	111	7.73
4 (Intermediate)	148	7.94
5 (Advanced)	85	5.64
6 (Expert)	95	6.41
Total	516	6.72

*Levels 1 and 7 excluded because of unavailability of hints.

D Illustrative Logic Tutor Proof Interaction

Figure 6–8 illustrates a representative student interaction in the propositional logic tutor. These screenshots demonstrate forward chaining, rule application, and goal completion within the tutor interface.

Figure 6: **Initial proof state and goal specification.** The student is presented with the premises (top left) and the target conclusion ($J \vee K$) at the bottom. Available inference rules are displayed on the middle. At this stage, no intermediate steps have been derived, and the student must choose a productive forward step toward the goal.

Figure 7: **Rule application with guided simplification.** After deriving an intermediate conjunction via Modus Ponens, the student applies the *Simplification* rule. The interface prompts the learner to select the appropriate resulting literal (G or $\neg H$), illustrating fine-grained, step-level decision making supported by rule constraints.

Figure 8: **Successful proof completion.** The student derives J via Disjunctive Syllogism and applies the *Addition* rule to reach the target conclusion $J \vee K$. The system confirms completion, reinforcing correct rule sequencing and alignment with the goal state.

E Representative Proof State

This appendix presents an illustrative propositional logic proof instance Fig 12 annotated with inter-

Figure 9: Over-validation (OV) and over-rejection (OR) rates by model across complexity tiers.

Figure 10: Over-validation (OV) and over-rejection (OR) rates by model across distance-to-goal tiers.

Figure 11: Classification F1 by inference rule and model. DS: Disjunctive Syllogism, HS: Hypothetical Syllogism, MP: Modus Ponens, CD: Constructive Dilemma, MT: Modus Tollens, Add: Addition, De Morgan's Law.

mediate derivations and agent-specific hints. Intermediate steps are derived by applying valid inference rules to previously established statements, with each step indexed and linked to its parent statements and rule application. This explicit structure exposes the shortest derivation path toward the conclusion while preserving alternative valid reasoning trajectories.

The Peer is provided only with the KG-verified

optimal next symbolic step, enabling guidance that focuses on local progression without access to derivational context. In contrast, the Teacher additionally receives the rule and parent statements used to derive this step, allowing feedback to reference structural reasoning without revealing the answer directly. This distinction isolates the effect of solution access: the Peer operates under minimal grounding, while the Teacher leverages full

Representative proof Instance	
Givens	
• (1) $((S \rightarrow Y) \vee (I * Q))$	
• (2) $((I \wedge Q) \rightarrow D)$	
• (3) $\neg D$	
• (4) $((S \rightarrow Y) \rightarrow D)$	
Intermediate Steps	
• (5) $\neg(S \rightarrow Y)$	[MT: (3), (4)]
• (6) $\neg(I \wedge Q)$	[MT: (3), (2)]
• (7) $(S \rightarrow Y)$	[DS: (6), (1)]
Conclusion: Y	
Peer Hint	
$\neg(\neg S \vee Y)$	
Teacher & Judge Hint	
Derive $\neg(\neg S \vee Y)$ from $\neg(S \rightarrow Y)$ using the Implication rule.	

Figure 12: Illustrative proof instance showing intermediate derivations and differential hint access for Peer and Teacher agents.

derivational context to support more informed intervention. The representative proof state is available in Fig 12.

F Knowledge Graph based Evaluation Metrics

This appendix provides formal definitions and illustrative examples of the graph-based metrics used to evaluate next-step reasoning quality. All metrics are computed with respect to the knowledge graph (KG) constructed for each problem.

F.1 Step Complexity

Beyond derivational validity, *Step Complexity* quantifies the intrinsic symbolic difficulty of a single inference step based on the structural complexity of the derived statement. We define step complexity as a function

$$c : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+,$$

computed directly from the syntactic structure of ϕ . Let $\mathcal{O}(\phi)$ denote the set of logical operators in ϕ ,

and let $\text{depth}(o)$ denote the nesting depth at which operator o occurs. The complexity of the step is defined as:

$$c(s_i, s_j) = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}(\phi)} w(o) \cdot \alpha^{\text{depth}(o)},$$

where $w(o)$ is an operator-specific base weight (e.g., $\neg, \wedge, \vee, \rightarrow, \leftrightarrow$) and $\alpha > 1$ controls the penalty for nested structure. For example, $c(F) < c(A + B) < c(A \rightarrow (B + C))$, because no operator is involved, only 1 operator is involved, and 2 operators involved along with nesting.

F.2 Distance to Conclusion

For any proof state $s \in \mathcal{S}$, its distance is defined as the length of the shortest derivation path to a terminal state s^* : $d(s) = \min_{\pi: s \rightsquigarrow s^*} |\pi|$ computed via breadth-first search over the KG. A predicted next step is considered *optimal* if it strictly reduces the distance to the goal by one.

Example If $d(s_t) = 4$ and a predicted successor state \hat{s}_{t+1} satisfies $d(\hat{s}_{t+1}) = 3$, the step is distance-optimal. A valid step leading to a state with $d(\hat{s}_{t+1}) = 5$ is considered a valid it is non-optimal.

G Implementation Details

Response Constraints. We standardize inference rule references using abbreviations (MP, MT, DS, HS, DeM, Impl) for consistent evaluation. The complete list appears in Table 3.

Token Limits. Rather than hard limits, we employ soft constraints via prompts (2–3 sentences).

Quality Validation. Two automated mechanisms ensure data integrity: (1) zero-token outputs trigger automatic retry, and (2) responses missing required JSON fields or violating constraints trigger re-prompting. Persistent failures after three attempts are flagged for manual review. Across 516 instances on 7 models, fewer than 3% required retry.

H Model Specifications

Please refer to Table 5.

Table 5: Models used in our experiments

Model	Org.	API	Context	Param
GPT-4.1	OpenAI	OpenAI	1M	-
GPT-o3	OpenAI	OpenAI	1M	-
Gemini 1.5 Pro	Google	Vertex	128K	-
Qwen-3-32B	Alibaba	Groq	32K	32B
LLaMA-3.3-70B	Meta	Groq	128K	70B
Mistral Large	Mistral	Mistral	256K	675B
Deepseek-r1-0528	Deepseek	Deepinfra	128K	671B

"-" refers to undisclosed

I Representative Examples of Failure Modes

Please refer to Figures 13, 14, and 17.

Proof state: 1. $((S \rightarrow Y) \vee (I \wedge Q))$, 2. $((I \wedge Q) \rightarrow D)$, 3. $\neg D$, 4. $((S \rightarrow Y) \rightarrow D)$, 5. $\neg(S \rightarrow Y)$, 6. $(I \wedge Q)$

Solution context : D

Reasoning: *Use Modus Tollens on $((S \rightarrow Y) \rightarrow D)$ and $\neg D$...*

Reasoning error: Incorrect rule

Peer Feedback: *"Great job on identifying Modus Tollens on $((S \rightarrow Y) \rightarrow D)$ and $\neg D$ as a key step. Now ask yourself, is there a step that could bridge your current progress to the CONCLUSION more efficiently..."*

Figure 13: Example for **Vague Peer Feedback** - repeats student's incorrect solution

Proof state: 1. $(B \leftrightarrow \neg J)$, 2. $(\neg N \vee J)$, 3. $(B \vee \neg N)$, 4. $((B \rightarrow \neg J) \wedge (\neg J \rightarrow B))$, 5. $(N \rightarrow J)$, 6. $(\neg B \rightarrow \neg N)$

Solution context: *Derive $(J \vee \neg N)$ from $(\neg N \vee J)$ using Commutative rule.*

Reasoning: *$(B \rightarrow \neg N)$ is optimal because it is the exact form of the conclusion, it can be derived from the contrapositive of $(\neg B \rightarrow \neg N)$...*

Reasoning error: Incorrect derivation

Teacher Feedback: *"Great job recognizing that $(B \rightarrow \neg N)$ is the contrapositive of $(\neg B \rightarrow \neg N)$ and using that to reach the conclusion..."*

Figure 14: Example for **Teacher feedback validating incorrect reasoning**

Proof state:

$(S > D) \vee I, (\neg S \vee Q) > Y, \neg D, \neg D > \neg I$

Simulated Student Response:

Reasoning: *MT on $\neg D > \neg I$ and $\neg D$ is needed to get $\neg I$ to be used later with $(S > D) \vee I$ for DS*

Next Step: $\neg I$

Rule Used: *MT*

Knowledge-Graph Correct Hint: Derive $\neg S$ from $(S > D)$ and $\neg D$ using *Modus Tollens (MT)*.

Teacher Feedback: *Great job identifying the relevant candidates! You correctly spotted that $(\neg D \rightarrow \neg I)$ and $\neg D$ could be useful, but there's a small mix-up with the rule. Recall: MT requires a negated *consequent*, while MP works with a *true antecedent*. How you might use MP on $(S > D)$ and $\neg D$ to get $\neg D$.*

Figure 15: Teacher (complete hint) feedback reveals solution on **incorrect** student response

Proof State (Excerpt)
 $(S \rightarrow D), ((\neg S \vee Q) \rightarrow Y), \neg D, (\neg D \rightarrow \neg I), \dots$

Simulated Student Response

Candidates:

- Simplify $S \rightarrow D$ to get $\neg S$
- ...

Reasoning: $\neg S$ is optimal because we already have $(S \rightarrow D)$ from INTERMEDIATE STEPS, and simplifying it to $\neg S$ allows us to construct $(\neg S \vee Q)$...

Rule: Simp

Peer Hint: $\neg S$

Peer Response

Peer Rule: Simp - echo failure

Student Assessment: Correct

Peer Feedback: *Excellent reasoning! You correctly identified how simplifying $(S \rightarrow D)$ helps set up the next step toward the conclusion...*

Judge Verification

Peer Feedback Correctness: Incorrect

Judge Action: Overridden Teacher Feedback

Final Judge Feedback: *Great job recognizing that you need $\neg S$ to proceed!, think about what rule you can use on $(S \rightarrow D)$ to turn it into a form more suitable for Simp...*

Figure 16: Judge Verification Response, extending Incorrect Peer feedback (anchoring on incorrect student reasoning)

Proof state: 1. $\neg(\neg G \wedge B)$, 2. $(G \rightarrow D)$

Solution context: Derive $(\neg\neg G \vee \neg B)$ from $\neg(\neg G \wedge B)$ using DeM Law.

Simulated Student reasoning: *Applying DN to $\neg(\neg G \wedge B)$ to get $(G \wedge B)$ is optimal because it directly gives us both G and B as available conjuncts...*

Reasoning error: Incorrect rule application

Peer Feedback: *"Great job applying double negation here! As you move forward, consider how you can use the new conjuncts to get closer..."*

Judge Feedback: *"You made a good attempt by considering double negation, but before applying DN, try using De Morgan's Law to rewrite..."*

Figure 17: Example for Judge Feedback repeating Peers' mistakes - also directs towards the hint without recognizing the reasoning error

I.1 Student Agent Response

We show a representative Student agent response to demonstrate candidate generation, explicit reasoning, and next-step generation. The example corresponds to a single proof instance and highlights how intermediate reasoning is externalized for downstream tutoring and verification. The sample response is shown in Fig 18.

Givens:
 $((\neg K \vee L) \rightarrow (M \wedge N)), (K \rightarrow O), \neg O$

Intermediates:
 $\neg K$ (MT: 2,3), $(\neg K \vee L)$ (Add: 4), $(M \wedge N)$ (MP: 1,5)

Conclusion: N

Student Response:

Candidate Steps:

- M : potentially useful for deriving N from $(M \wedge N)$.
- $\neg M$: less direct without a clear derivation.
- $(M \wedge N)$: already derived; insufficient alone to reach N .

Reasoning: Applying a rule directly to $(M \wedge N)$ is the most efficient path to the conclusion. Since $(M \wedge N)$ is available, simplification yields the target.

Next Step: N

Rule: Simp

Parent Statement: $(M \wedge N)$

Figure 18: Sample problem instance and corresponding correct student response

J Prompt Design

This section provides the complete prompts used for each agent in our multi-agent tutoring system. All prompts use structured JSON response formats to ensure consistent parsing.

Our prompt design translates established pedagogical principles into operational constraints for LLM agents. Each agent’s prompt encodes specific instructional strategies grounded in learning science research, ensuring that generated feedback aligns with effective tutoring practices. We describe the key design decisions below.

J.1 Student Prompt

The base system message includes the Role and Task information along with instructions, whereas the user message includes the problem instance itself. The prompt template is provided below in Fig 19.

Student Simulation Prompt

Role: You are a Student in an undergraduate Discrete Structures course solving a propositional logic proof. Your task is to produce the *single most optimal next step* that advances the proof toward the conclusion.

Task:

1. Review the givens and intermediate steps.
2. Propose 2–3 candidate next steps.
3. Select the candidate that most directly advances toward the conclusion.
4. Justify your choice and output the selected next step.

Constraints:

- Output exactly one next step in *symbolic notation only*.
- Use only predefined inference rules (e.g., MP, MT, Conj, DS).
- Parent statements must be actual expressions, not line numbers.

Response Format:

- CANDIDATES: 2–3 candidate steps with brief justification
- REASONING: Why the selected step is optimal
- NEXT_STEP: Symbolic expression
- RULE: Inference rule (short name)
- PARENT_STATEMENTS: Supporting expressions

Figure 19: Base System Prompt for Student

J.2 Peer Prompt

The Peer operates under *minimal hint access*: it receives only the correct next step without knowledge of the complete solution path. The prompt enforces a critical **planning-before-feedback** requirement: the Peer must first generate an internal derivation plan explaining how the correct step is derived (identifying the rule and parent statements) before producing student-facing feedback. This de-

sign decision ensures the Peer develops a genuine understanding of the solution rather than pattern-matching, aligning with research showing that scaffolded feedback improves instructional quality (Serban et al., 2020). The prompt is illustrated in Fig 20.

J.3 Teacher Prompt

The Teacher agent has access to the complete next step and provides scaffolded feedback without revealing the answer. The prompt is illustrated in Fig 21.

J.4 Judge Prompt

The Judge agent is tasked with thoroughly evaluating both the student’s and the teacher’s responses to the logic proof problem. While the Teacher has access to the correct step and is therefore not asked to verify its own guidance, the Judge is specifically instructed to examine and identify any errors or inaccuracies present in both the student’s and the teacher’s responses.

Equipped with comprehensive access to the correct derivation steps from the knowledge base, the Judge carefully analyzes the reasoning behind both responses. Its role is to provide targeted evaluations and, where necessary, concise and actionable feedback to ensure alignment with the correct logic step. This approach ensures a robust layer of verification and strengthens the overall quality and pedagogical value of the feedback offered to the student. The prompt is illustrated in Fig 22.

Table 6: Rubric for evaluating pedagogical quality of agent-generated feedback.

Dimension	Score 1: Low	Score 2: Moderate	Score 3: High
Correctness	Contains errors that would mislead the student	Minor imprecisions but no fundamental errors	All statements are logically and factually accurate
Error Identification	Fails to identify the error or identifies incorrectly	Indicates error exists but identification is vague	Precisely identifies the specific error; affirms correctness if applicable
Revealing	Guides without revealing, using scaffolding or Socratic questioning	Hints at solution direction without explicit disclosure	Discloses solution content explicitly (names rule, states next step)
Actionability	No actionable guidance; student cannot proceed	General guidance but lacks specificity	Clear, specific guidance enabling appropriate next step

Peer Prompt

Role: You are a Peer evaluating a student's proposed next step in a propositional logic proof, with access to the KG-derived optimal step.

Task:

1. Analyze how the optimal step is derived (rule and parent statements).
2. Evaluate the student's candidates, reasoning, and chosen next step.
3. Classify the student's step as *Correct*, *Valid Alternative*, or *Incorrect*.
4. Provide brief, scaffolded feedback guiding the student toward the optimal step.

Constraints:

- Do not reveal the optimal step, its rule, or parent statements.
- Acknowledge what the student did correctly before addressing errors.
- Use Socratic questions to guide reasoning; keep feedback concise (2–3 sentences).
- Use predefined inference rule short names only.

Response Format:

- STUDENT_ERRORS: Brief explanation or Correct
- NEXT_STEP_CORRECTNESS: Correct / Suboptimal / Incorrect
- PEER_FEEDBACK: Scaffolded guidance without answer revelation

Figure 20: Base System prompt for Peer

Teacher Prompt

Role: You are a Teacher evaluating a student's proposed next step in a propositional logic proof, with access to the complete solution (KNOWLEDGE_BASE_STEPS).

Task:

1. Compare the student's response against the knowledge-base solution.
2. Identify errors in the student's logic, rule usage, or reasoning.
3. Classify the student's next step as *Correct*, *Valid Alternative*, or *Incorrect*.
4. Provide brief, scaffolded feedback guiding the student toward the correct solution.

Constraints:

- Do not reveal the exact next step, rule, or parent statements from the solution.
- Acknowledge correct aspects of the student's attempt before addressing errors.
- Use Socratic questions to guide reasoning; keep feedback concise (2–3 sentences).
- Refer to the student's candidates when relevant.
- Use predefined inference rule short names only.

Response Format:

- STUDENT_ERRORS: Brief explanation or Correct
- NEXT_STEP_CORRECTNESS: Correct / Suboptimal / Incorrect
- TEACHER_FEEDBACK: Scaffolded guidance without answer revelation

Figure 21: Base System prompt for Teacher

Judge (Verifier) Prompt

Role: You are an expert pedagogical AI Judge for propositional logic proof problems, with access to the complete solution (KNOWLEDGE_BASE_STEPS). You evaluate both the student's proposed next step and the Teacher's feedback.

Task:

1. Compare the student's response against the knowledge-base solution.
2. Identify errors in the student's reasoning, if any.
3. Classify the student's next step as *Correct*, *Valid Alternative*, or *Incorrect*.
4. Evaluate whether the Teacher's feedback correctly guides the student.
5. Either enhance the Teacher's feedback or override it with corrected guidance.

Constraints:

- Do not reveal the exact next step, rule, or parent statements from the solution.
- Acknowledge correct aspects of the student's attempt before addressing errors.
- Use Socratic questions to guide reasoning; scaffold rather than instruct.
- Override Teacher feedback if it is incorrect, misleading, or reveals the solution.
- Keep final feedback concise (2–3 sentences) and encouraging.
- Use predefined inference rule short names only.

Response Format:

- STUDENT_ERRORS: Brief explanation or Correct
- NEXT_STEP_CORRECTNESS: Correct / Suboptimal / Incorrect
- TEACHER_FEEDBACK_CORRECTNESS: Assessment of Teacher feedback
- JUDGE_ACTION: Enhanced or Overridden
- FINAL_FEEDBACK: Judge-approved scaffolded guidance

Figure 22: Base System prompt for Judge